

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MAGULLO****FIRST NAME: Bezu****PROGRAM CODE : DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401/ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: PR1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium)

The author used the following software: MS Word 365, Window 10/11

The 5 key concepts with page number

1. Overview of Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7)
2. Basic process of Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-34)
3. Rules of Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 13)
4. Basic Style guide of Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 41)
5. Review of response paper

ACADAMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

To start this course, I took plenty of my time at the biggening as I was very confused where and how to start about it even though I read and explored a lot of source information from Euclid university website. After confirmation of my registration, I received some important documents including initial studentorientation,2022, templates, checklists and sample of response paper by the International Admissions team; and others by the assigned instructor Dr. Kabiru. That really helped me to calm down and focused.

Following to the review of all the documents, I came to the first part of my course coded ACA-401/ACA-401D. I read the given course pack and carefully reviewed. The course pack has eight revised chapters in away easily to understand and practical both at academic level and the day today program activities. It is very helpful; and I enjoyed reading it. At the end of the course, I have focused and summarized on five basic areas including: a) Overview of Essay writing b) Rules of Essay writing c) Basic Essay writing d) review of response paper which are well explained bellow.

2) **ESSAY WRITING**

After careful review of the essay writing part of the course pack, I found that it is the most important for the next courses and important for my routine activities too. I have been working in non-Governmental organization since 2006 including WHO. I usually prepare technical report at the end of every month, quarter and year. However, after I read this course pack, I realized that I should improve a lot of areas on my technical report. It is very reasonable to bring up this course at the first parts of the program. It helps for the subsequent courses. The course pack is well explained, simple to understand. However, I still believe it needs to be further review especially the punctuation and language variance part of the course pack. Finally, I extracted and organized the course-pack in five main areas as bellow.

a) Overview of essay writing

We know that there are many types of essays. But, for the purpose of the given course, I will focus on academic essay writing. Academic essay or scholarship is nonfictional writing that intended for academic purposes as part of academic work. It always aims to provide evidence-based answers to certain hypothesis (EUCLID 2021, 7). There are different types of academic writings including research findings, theses, manuscripts, literature review, newspapers, conference papers, books, technical reports etc. Almost all of them are shared basic rules, concepts, features, and process (EUCLID 2021, 7).

b) Basic process of essay writing

To prepare effective and well-organized academic essay, we should follow basic steps starting from the beginning to an end. It is very important to shorten time and to be focused. In the process of essay writing there are basic steps to be considered by the author including:

i) Starting time and researching the Topic

It is advisable to initiate the essay writing as early as possible (EUCLID 2021, 7). This will help for writing to have good time to read, research the right topic, and explore more and write. After selecting the topic, it is time now to define the questions, analyzing the tasks and then develop a plan and to write (EUCLID 2021, 7).

ii) Organizing ideas and writing the Essay

As you are developing the first draft of the essay, it is very important to use the given format. After the draft first draft it must be refined and edited to make sure that well-structured, framed, good content and flow of idea in a way to meet set objectives (EUCLID

2021, 7-9). I really like the flow of idea of this course pack and the rational why it comes at the first part of all the other courses. Commonly, all essays have three main parts including: Introduction, body and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 7). Any ideas coming to your mind should be included as per this format so that the reader can easily grasp the content of the specific essay.

iii) *Referencing the essay*

It is must to include references in any academic essays to provide credit for the source information (EUCLID 2021, 11). Reference protects against plagiarisms which may lead to serious academic offense (EUCLID 2021, 11). Plagiarism is simply used writer source information without giving credit to the author of original information (EUCLID 2021, 34). The source might be words, ideas, paraphrasing, or it might be copying and pasting from the internet (EUCLID 2021, 34). So, it is must to cite reference in order to safeguard ourselves. It is also very important to follow the standard referencing style or format throughout the essay. Plagiarism is unethical, a serious academic offense that will lead serious consequences (EUCLID 2021, 34). In this part I learnt a lot how to cite references and importance of it.

c) Rules of essay writing

There are some rules that every academic essay should follow. It can help the essay to be focused and scientific. Some of the rules include state the main hypotheses of your essay at the beginning, stay always focused, make your essay clear and concise, and avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 13). To make sure your essay has captured some of the basic rules it is advisable to allocate some time for editing or seek your colleague or friend help to read it for constructive feedback if that is feasible for you.

d) Basic Style guide of Essay Writing

Style guide is one of the most important part that every author should follow based on the advised style. It is important to ensure that the writing is consistent and a means of documenting writer approach. It makes your essay to be more clear may be much more than correct use of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary (EUCLID 2021, 41). Some of the elements of style guide includes use of headings, paragraph numbering and indentation, structure, preferences voices, symbols use, use of abbreviations, spelling, use of fonts, sentence length, layout (EUCLID 2021, 41).

e) Response paper review

This is one of the important parts I learnt from this course. It is necessary to review students' response paper systematically. From Dr. Kabiru's You Tube channel, I learnt a lot how to review students' paper. The review includes proper use of spelling, punctuation,

grammar, style, spacing, reference citation. Then finally, send back to the specific student for correction and resend to the instructor.

3) **CONCLUSION**

Even though there was a lot of confusion, frustration and unfocused at the beginning of this course, finally I end up with a good understanding of the specific course. This course is very important and helpful for our routine technical reports too. The course pack is well organized, straight forward to understand the course pack. Using the course pack review, I have extracted five basic areas to be focused and easy to understand including the basic process, rules, style guide and finally how to systematically review student response papers. The course is generally very helpful and friendly. So, I really recommend everyone to explore and approach this course.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

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